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Challenges of the medical physicist in pediatric radiation oncology

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Abstract

Although there is no doubt about the effectiveness of radiotherapy in the treatment of pediatric oncological patients, the specific radio-sensitivity of children and the young population can compromise the further quality of patient's life and even adversely affects overall survival statistics. Therefore, in addition to reducing the total tumor dose, daily dose and target volume in pediatric radiotherapy, the treatment plan must be achieved by strongly minimizing the total body volume exposed to radiation.

This is a critical goal, considering the increased risk of secondary malignancies in cancer survivors who were treated with radiotherapy in childhood, but this can be in conflict with the need for some tissue dose homogenization, which is important in pediatrics due to the proper growth and development of children. Consequently, the therapy dose distribution in young patients can differ from dose distributions optimal for adults. Pediatric radiotherapy plans cover various regions of the body with diagnoses that are often not found in adult patients.

We should be cautious in introducing modern technology in pediatrics. With highly conformal techniques, such as IMRT and fast VMAT treatments, we risk delivering low doses to a significant body volume. The same applies to the proton radiotherapy, with all the advantages it has in sparing normal tissue.

In the quality control of radiotherapy treatment, it is of particular importance to optimize imaging protocols and IGRT procedures according to children.

The tasks of a medical physicist in pediatrics are, finally, influenced by responsibility in treating a young population which requires well-developed communication in all pediatric teamwork.

Keywords: radiotherapy, childhood, dose distribution

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